

**THE ROLE OF THE FEMALE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS
IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.**

Bekbo`tayeva S.T student.

Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport.

Chirchiq, Uzbekistan.

*"We are willing to serve sincerely so that women can live with pleasure and
satisfaction" SH. Mirziyoyev*

Annotation: This article focuses on the role of the female physical education teachers in educational institutions in our country and the importance of their work. Medical physiological and psychological changes in high school girls have led to their low participation in physical education classes as a predisposition. This is a sign that our educational institutions need female physical education teachers at a significant level. An increase the number of female trainers; is a great factor to widespread involvement of girls in sports, an organizing the healthy lifestyle among them, and the promotion of sport among young generation. The rise of female trainers: widespread involvement of girls in sports, the organization of a healthy lifestyle among them, and the promotion of sports are a great factor. After all, the emphasis on the health of women and girls is the main criterion for bringing up a healthy generation in our country.

Keyword: Physical development, physical education, physical culture, sports healthy lifestyle, women's and girls` sports.

The indicators that determine the strength and well-being of any country are also determined by generations who are mature, physically healthy, and perfect in all respects that will reach perfection in this country. From this point of view, raising a physically healthy and perfect generation in our country has

become one of the most important tasks of our government's policy. Anyone grows up in a family, is raised in it. In this case, women are directly responsible for raising children. So, only a spiritually and physically healthy woman can raise a healthy and energetic child.

After our country gained independence, the emphasis on women and girls in our country increased day by day, showing respect for women, protecting them in every situation, creating conditions for them to live a healthy life and happiness has become one of the most pressing issues. In particular, attracting women and girls to sports, creating the necessary opportunities for them to engage in public sports, is the most important task. In this regard, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Physical Education and Sports, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the development of physical education and sports" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF - 5924 of January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and promote physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" serves as a legal foundation of all these improvements.

Today, a wide range of reforms have been implemented in our country and society in every areas and fields. It is also appropriate to note a number of changes in education. It is no secret achievements that attained in the quality of physical education but also there are shortcomings in this in conjunction in secondary schools. In the effective organization of physical education classes in remote parts of our country, it is unfortunate that first and foremost, there are no gymnasiums and that existing ones are required to be renovated. Also troubling to us is that it is an issue facing 9th, 10th and 11th grade girls in secondary schools. It is well-known that because of the shortage of female physical education teachers in secondary schools, especially in educational institutions far from the district center, high school girls are less attracted to physical education classes because of their natural physiological and psychological changes. Finding a positive solution to existing problems is the most important

task facing leaders working in the field of our government and the education system.

Established on October 24, 2002, the Children's Sports Development Fund (Children's Sports Development Association) built sport halls where equipped with modern sports equipments in remote parts of our country is the solution for the first issue, while physical education classes in secondary schools have been taught separately to boys and girls since grade 8, and female teacher provide lessons for schoolgirls, as well as the resolution adopted on April 1, 2010 "On measures to stimulate the work of female sports teachers engaged in children's sports facilities in rural areas" active involvement of girls, especially schoolgirls in rural areas in sports, to train highly qualified professional women's teaching staff for children's sports facilities, is considered an important factor in providing financial support to their work.

At the same time, starting in the 2020-2021 academic year, an increase in the acceptance quota in higher education institutions and the allocation of separate quotas for girls are the result of the great opportunities given to women and girls in our country.

It is no secret that the women and girls of our country, together with leadership in any area of our society in general, are sincerely carrying out the difficult tasks entrusted to them. Including female physical education teachers, curators, and our female trainers in educational institutions, such as Dilfuza Rahmatova (national wrestling), Lilia Vlasova (artistic gymnastics), Dilnoza Bakirova (Karate WKF), Saida Maxmudova (table tennis), take responsibility for their work, that they organize the learning process efficiently, that they are conducting sports at a high level become a cause of grown up many champion girls in world arenas today who contribute to the raising of our country's flag and the sound of the our national anthem. The rise of female trainers is an important factor in attracting girls to sports, organizing healthy lifestyles among them, and promoting sports. Furthermore, the emphasis on the health of

women's girls` is the main mechanism for bringing up a healthy generation in our country.

List of used publications.

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Physical Education and Sports.
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the development of physical education and sports".
3. Resolution PQ-1315 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to stimulate the work of female sports teachers engaged in children's sports facilities in rural areas"
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No UP-5924 of January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and promote physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan".
5. Salomov R.S. Theory and methodology of physical education. - T., 2015.